

A toolset to detect and classify Active Deformation Areas using interferometric SAR data

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Abstract: The MOMIT project is targeted at showing how remote sensing techniques may help to monitor and then maintain railway infrastructures. This project has defined several demonstrators to fulfill such goal. The authors have been involved in the design and development of several software tools needed to implement the first demonstrator, dealing with ground movements nearby the railway infrastructures. Among these tools, ADAfinder, ADAclassifier and los2hv have been developed at the CTTC. The aim of ADAfinder is to detect—and update— areas where active deformation processes are taking place; ADAclassifier is targeted at identifying the kind of processes undergone by such areas; finally, los2hv is a tool computing the horizontal and vertical components of the movement measured along a line of sight. This paper takes care of describing these three application, in the context of the MOMIT project, not forgetting the benefits derived from the automation of the methodologies they rely on. The formal testing process of the tools as well as some results obtained with real datasets are also presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The MOMIT project—(Multi-scale Observation and Monitoring of railway Infrastructure Threats), see (MOMIT, 2017) for details—aims at developing and demonstrating a new use of remote sensing technologies for railway infrastructures monitoring. MOMIT solutions will mainly aim at supporting the maintenance and prevention processes within the infrastructure management lifecycle. The overall concept underpinning MOMIT project is the demonstration of the benefits brought by Earth Observation and Remote Sensing to the monitoring of railways networks both in terms of the infrastructure and of the surrounding environment, where activities and phenomena impacting the infrastructure could be present. MOMIT will leverage on state of the art technologies in the fields of space-based remote sensing and RPAS (Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems) based to perform different kind of analysis thanks to the wide variety of sensors they could be equipped with.

To achieve its goals, six demonstrators showing how these data and technologies may contribute to such objectives are being built, namely:

1. Ground movements nearby the infrastructure.
2. Hydraulic activities nearby the track.
3. Global supervision for natural hazards.
4. Electrical system monitoring.
5. Civil engineering structures monitoring.
6. Safety monitoring.

The Division of Geomatics of the CTTC (Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya) takes care of building some of the components integrating the first demonstrator, whose objectives are detailed in (MOMIT, 2017). The goal most relevant to the work presented here is to use the PSI (Persistent Scatterer Interferometry) method for monitoring the sites of interest, allowing the measurement of differential deformation of the ground and each single structure, with millimetric / centimetric precision.

Several software applications are needed in the context of this demonstrator. This paper describes those developed at CTTC, namely, ADAfinder, ADAclassifier and los2hv. The first one, ADAfinder, is a tool to detect and update ADAs (Active Deformation Areas) using Sentinel-1 imagery and PSI. The

main goal of such application is to update and assess the geohazard activity (volcanic activity, landslides or ground subsidence among other phenomena) of a given area. ADAclassifier goes a step beyond ADAfinder, trying to classify the kind of deformation process undergone by the ADAs — that is, is the detected deformation process a landslide, a sinkhole, or what else? Finally, los2hv computes the horizontal and vertical components of the movement measured along the LOS (Line Of Sight). The horizontal component of such movement is one of the inputs of ADAclassifier; therefore, a tool to compute it was needed.

2 AUTOMATING METHODOLOGIES

The three tools presented in this paper rely in pre-existing methodologies, that is, these applications have *automated* a set of procedures that already existed.

In the case of ADAfinder, a methodology to perform the identification and assessment of ADAs was presented in (Barra et al., 2017) back in 2017. In that work, the authors explain in detail the procedure to identify the active deformation areas and also to assess the certainty of such findings; the set of points making each ADA as well as its area of influence and the quality index stating the goodness of the assessment are the most relevant outputs. The input, the set of PSs (Persistent Scatterers, *aka* the points) covering the area to analyze.

ADAclassifier relies on a methodology that is under active research—although mature enough as to be automated, thus easing the experimentation in this area and helping to improve the methodology itself. For more details, see (Tomás et al., 2018).

Finally, the work described in (Notti et al., 2014) is the base of the implementation of los2hv.

The aforementioned procedures usually rely on the heavy use of a GIS (Geographic Information System) tool and the expertise of its operator; therefore, these are *time-consuming*, *error-prone processes*, which require *qualified* human resources.

This paper presents an implementation of the three methodologies and algorithms above, incarnated as the above-mentioned ADAfinder, ADAclassifier and los2hv applications. The goals of such implementations are (1) to automate the respective procedures to avoid unnecessary human errors, (2) to reduce the time needed to identify and preclassify the ADAs, thus opening the door to more frequent updates and analysis, and (3) to reduce the expertise required to obtain such results, being possible to integrate the

process in an semi-automated production workflow, if necessary and possible.

3 THE APPLICATIONS

3.1 ADAfinder

The first tool in the set is ADAfinder. This application is used to identify those areas that are undergoing a deformation process, whatever it is. Additionally, an assessment of the quality of the detection process is performed.

As inputs, it takes:

- An ESRI shapefile containing the PSs that will be used by the detection algorithm. ADAfinder needs the attributes related to these PSs to be, at least, the coordinates of the points, their velocity, and the deformation time series measuring the movements undergone by the PSs at various times in the past.
- Optionally, another shapefile defining a polygon delimiting the area of interest to be analyzed. All PSs in the input shapefile are taken into account when such polygon is not provided.
- The set of parameters defined by the methodology described in (Barra et al., 2017).

The output is made of two ESRI shapefiles, the first one containing the polygons defining the boundaries of the ADAs; the other contains the set of PSs passing the set of filters set by the methodology.

Figure 1 depicts the user interface of the GUI (Graphical User Interface) version of the ADAfinder tool.

The output ADA shapefile includes among its attributes the results of the quality assessment of the deformation detection process. Such assessment is represented by a four-level variable whose values measure the certainty ("very sure", "sure", "not so sure" and "not sure at all") of the deformation detection process. Figure 2 shows some ADAs; their colours correspond to just two of the certainty levels described ("very sure", green, "sure", blue).

For more details on the ADAfinder tool, please refer to (Navarro et al., 2018a) and (Navarro and Cuevas, 2018b).

3.2 ADAclassifier

The second application in the toolset is ADAclassifier. This tool takes the output of ADAfinder, that is,

Figure 1: The GUI version of the ADAfinder tool.

Figure 2: An example of the output of ADAfinder. Colours are used to show the quality assessment.

a set of ADAs, and tries to determine the kind(s) of deformation process(es) undergone by each of them.

Up to six different kinds of deformation phenomena are detected. These are: landslides, sinkholes, land subsidences, constructive or consolidation settlements, expansive soils and temperature effects. A different algorithm (or sub-methodology) has been devised for each of these. For instance, Figure 3 roughly depicts how landslides are detected.

Being able to detect so many kind of deformation processes implies that ADAclassifier needs a substantial number of inputs. These are:

- The ADAs and PSs files created by ADAfinder (see section 3.1). Obviously, these files need not to be created by ADAfinder, but the set of attributes must match those required by ADAclassifier—and that ADAfinder does include in its output.

Figure 3: Algorithm to detect landslides.

- A DTM (Digital Terrain Model), to compute slopes.
- A series of polygon vector maps (*inventories* from now on,) in the form of ESRI shapefiles, to check whether an ADA has already being catalogued as belonging to any of the six aforementioned deformation processes. The required inventories are those for landslides, sinkholes, land subsidences, infrastructures. A geologic map (another polygon vector map) is also needed.
- Again, an ESRI (polygon) shapefile storing the horizontal component of the movement for the study area. This is, typically, the output of los2hv (see section 3.3 for details).
- Finally, the set of parameters—typically thresholds—needed by the different algorithms in charge of the classification processes must be supplied. Examples of such parameters are slopes, Pearson coefficients to state whether some statistical check is positive, or the minimum percentage of overlap of an ADA and the polygons in some inventory to consider that they do intersect.

The output of ADAclassifier is another file with ADAS, where the set of attributes characterizing each of them has been extended to include six more. Each of them state the possibility that the ADA belongs to the corresponding deformation process. This is so because *all* the detection algorithms are applied to each ADA. Therefore, and although incongruous, some ADAs might be classified as positives in more than one deformation process.

Four levels of certainty are defined by the methodology: "it is an X", "it could be an X", "it is not an X" and "X has not been checked", where "X" stands for

each of the six deformation detection processes executed by ADAclassifier—for instance, when talking about landslides, “it is a landslide” would be one of the values of the corresponding attribute.

Note that one of the four values is “not checked”. This is so because ADAclassifier may decide not to apply one or more of the six detection processes because of the lack of data. As stated above, a noticeable number of inputs is required. Just the inventory files already amount to five. Taking also into account the DTM and the horizontal components of the movement, it is easy to realize that many will be the situations when the full set of files will *not* be available.

To alleviate this usual problem, ADAclassifier makes optional almost every input file (this includes the DTM, the inventories and the horizontal components). Each time the application is run, it analyzes the dependencies of each sub-algorithm and decides which of these may be executed as a function of the inputs provided by the user. Consequently, it is necessary to add the “not checked” value as one of the possible outputs of each classification process. Note that this behaviour makes the tool much more flexible: while concentrating the detection of six deformation processes in a single application, it may be used to check only one of these, just providing the available set of data.

The ADAclassifier tool is described in more detail in (Navarro et al., 2018b).

3.3 Los2hv

The los2hv tool is targeted at the computation of the separate horizontal and vertical components of the ground displacement measured with PSI technologies along the satellite’s LOS. Both ascending and descending datasets—that is, files with PSs derived from SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) images captured when the satellite is traveling from south to north and from north to south respectively—are required. los2hv, in its current version, is not able to compute such horizontal and vertical components when only one dataset (ascending or descending) is available.

The tool accepts (input) and produces (output) ESRI shapefiles for compatibility reasons. On output, los2hv creates two files, to store, respectively, the horizontal and vertical components of the movement as observed along the LOS.

los2hv performs a tessellation of the whole area covered by the PSs included in the two input files. The size of the tesserae (grid spacing) is decided by the user. As a consequence, each PS belongs to one of the resulting tesserae.

Figure 4: los2v: tesserae and ascending and descending PSs.

There may be tesserae where (1) there are no PSs, (2) there are only PSs from the ascending input file, (3) there are only PSs from the descending input file and, finally (4) there are PSs from both input files (see Figure 4). For those tesserae of type (4), the ground movement is averaged. The resulting amount, measured along the LOS, is then converted to horizontal and vertical components according to the formulae described in (Notti et al., 2014). The value of the horizontal and vertical components of the ground movement corresponds now to the whole area covered by the tessera where the points involved in the computation were located.

These values are saved to the corresponding output files. Note that the user may select to store points (centroids of the tesserae with data) or squares (boundaries of the tesserae). The second kind of output (squares) is the one used by ADAclassifier. The centroid output is provided for whatever other purposes.

For more information about los2hv, please refer to (Navarro and Cuevas, 2018a).

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION

4.1 The Language of Choice

The toolset has been implemented in C++ to boost performance. Other popular languages, as Python, have been avoided precisely for that reason. Although developed using Microsoft’s Visual Studio, special precautions have been taken to make the source code portable, particularly for the most popular C++ compiler used in the Linux operating system, i.e. gcc.

Choosing C++ opened the door to using several

open source libraries on which the toolset relies. The most relevant ones are:

- Qt. Although it has been used for several purposes, the main target was to provide a portable GUI for the three applications.
- Shapelib. This library is a very convenient tool to read and write ESRI shapefiles.
- Clipper. A library for clipping and offsetting lines and polygons.

The selection of the programming language has direct implications on how the logic of these applications may be embedded in other software components. See section 4.2 for further details.

4.2 Three Flavours

Each of the applications described in section 3 are available in three different incarnations or flavours:

- As a C++ class in a *library* (one for each application). Third party (C++) software willing to embed the logic of ADAfinder, ADAclassifier or los2hv as a black box, only needs to instantiate the corresponding class. Thus, embedding the necessary logic to be able to identify or classify ADAs or to compute the horizontal components of the movement is just one procedure call away. Obviously, only software components developed in C++ will be able to integrate the logic in the library.
- As a *command-line utility*. This makes possible to integrate these tools in batch workflows, since no human intervention is required to run them. See section 4.3 for details on options files, the mechanism used to obtain the information controlling the behaviour of the applications.
- As an *application featuring a GUI*. This flavour is the best one for experimenting because of its ease of use. GUI-based applications, however, cannot be integrated in batch workflows.

Note that the command-line as well as the GUI versions of the applications are just interfaces calling the classes in the library that actually implement the logic of the processes.

4.3 Option Files

Both the command-line and GUI versions of the applications in the toolset rely on option files to retrieve the information defining how to proceed—input or output files, thresholds controlling some condition, etc. Note that this is so for the GUI-based tools too; in fact, the GUI is just a mechanism to fill the gaps in

an option file template. This simplifies the design of the classes implementing the logic, since only one interface (the option file) needs to be taken care of. The command-line incarnations of the three tools have a single parameter: the name of the options file with the program's parameters.

The option files used by the toolset are uncomplicated, plain text files including pairs of labels and values:

```
POSITION_X = 5
```

4.4 Real-life Shapefiles

ESRI shapefiles, although standardized, may include variable sets of attributes. Even when a shapefile includes the full set of attributes needed by a tool (for instance, the x and y coordinates as well as the velocity or the deformation time series in the case of ADAfinder), they may appear in different columns of the attribute (.dbf) file. This usually depends on the provider of the files.

This variability might become a serious problem, since the input module should be adapted for each kind of shapefile to process.

The solution to avoid this problem are the "read-map files" defining how the relevant attributes in a shapefile are organized. Of course, the attributes needed by the tools to work properly must always be present in the files, but thanks to these read-map files it is possible to deal with changes in the positions where these appear.

Thus, a read-map file is just an extra options file (see section 4.3) where, by means of couples of labels and values, the positions of the attributes on which each tool rely are specified.

Such a simple mechanism makes the toolset much more flexible and able to deal with real-life datasets.

5 QUALITY ASSURANCE

Prior to the delivery of the tools to the MOMIT consortium, these went through a rigorous testing process to guarantee that they worked correctly. Note that both a test plan and a test report concerning the whole toolset are described, respectively, in (Navarro et al., 2018c) and (Navarro et al., 2018d). There, the full details on how testing was devised and took place are provided. However, and for the sake of completeness, the next sections briefly presents the most relevant steps taken to guarantee the quality of the code.

In the case of ADAfinder, the manual methodology had been used for some time in GIS environments when this tool was developed, so datasets including

both inputs and outputs were available. Therefore, the tests consisted essentially in comparing the results of the manual procedure with those created by the tool.

A mechanism to quickly compare the results produced by the manual and automated solutions was devised; basically, it consisted on exporting the values of the attributes to check for both outputs (manual and automated), sorting these to easily match the attributes in each file and then computing the differences of their values, which, in all cases, were under the threshold set by the precision of the typical 8-byte IEEE 754 double (around the 15th decimal position). This means, from the numerical standpoint, that the results (for instance, the coordinates of the output points) were equivalent. The values of the attributes standing the level of certainty were checked for absolute equality since these were represented by integer (non-floating point) magnitudes.

The situation of ADAclassifier and los2hv was different; no previous results existed, so no reliable dataset to compare their outputs was at hand. The approach, therefore, was to create synthetic datasets for both applications. The rationale behind the way these datasets were created was to organize the information in easily identifiable geometric patterns, so, when combined, the area(s) where positive results lie is (are) also predictable. For instance, all ADAS were identical square-shaped polygons distributed in a 24×24 ADAs checkerboard pattern (see Figure 5a); the horizontal components of the moment were distributed in 4 adjacent vertical stripes covering 6×24 ADAs each and setting a known value to each of them (0, 10, 20 and 30 mm/year respectively) as shown in Figure 5b. Other easily identifiable patterns were used for the rest of input files.

Then, for example, assuming that some classification process needs the value of the horizontal component of the movement to be higher than 25 mm/year, then only the rightmost column made of 6×24 ADAs will meet the requirement. This may be seen in Figure 5c where the ADAs and the horizontal components of the movement (figures 5a and 5b) have been overlapped.

6 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Only one of the applications developed and tested, ADAfinder, relies on a procedure for which previous results already existed. Therefore, it was the only one for which a performance reference was available to compare with. Since such procedure was executed manually (a series of steps performed by an operator using the tools offered by a GIS) a noticeable im-

Figure 5: ADAclassifier: synthetic dataset samples.

Tool	Dataset	Time (s)
ADAfinder	20,351 PSs.	2
ADAfinder	926,916 PSs.	179
ADAclassifier	144 ADAs, 3600 PSs, between 4 - 8 polygons per inventory, DTM with 1441×1441 z values.	125
los2hv	2×135 PSs. Grid: 7×7 tesserae.	55

Table 1: Performance of the several tools.

provement of performance was expected due to automation.

There were no performance references for the two other tools (los2hv and ADAclassifier) so no specific expectations about performance improvements existed. All tests took place using a computer with the following characteristics: Windows 10 64-bit, Intel Core i5-5300U @ 2.3 GHz, 2 cores, 4 threads, 8 Gb RAM, 500 Gb magnetic (non-SSD) hard disk. Table 1 shows the performance of the three tools.

Note that in the case of ADAclassifier, the process includes the identification of *six* different classes of deformation phenomena (that is, the test covers all the possible classification processes available). Testing for fewer options will reduce the time needed to process data.

Figure 6: ADAfinder. Results for the Tenerife dataset (source: (Barra et al., 2017)).

7 REAL TEST CASES

As stated in section 5, two real datasets were used to check the correctness of the ADAfinder application. The first one corresponds to Tenerife, one of the Canary Islands; the other one, the Glòries dataset covers one of the neighbourhoods of the city of Barcelona. The results related to the most representative one, Tenerife, are briefly presented here. Glòries is a very small dataset, containing only 20351 PSs only and covering a much smaller area, so it was used primarily to test the correctness of the application taking almost no time to obtain results (about 2 s); it will not be presented here.

The main parameters defining the dataset and how it was processed follow (please, refer to (Barra et al., 2017) for a detailed description of their meaning):

- Number of PSs in the input file: 926,916.
- Standard deviation of the velocity of the whole set of PSs (σ_v): 2.35 mm/year. The factor to apply to σ_v to obtain the stable/ moving threshold: 2.
- Points are considered isolated when having only 1 or no neighbours.
- Minimum set of a cluster of points to be an ADA candidate: 5.
- ADA radius: 40 m.

The results are shown in Figures 6a and 6b. The left side of the figure depicts the distribution of PSs and their velocities. On the right side, the 72 ADAs detected by ADAfinder are shown. Note the QI (quality index) values is measuring the reliability (certainty) of the detection process. The meanings of these values are: (1, red): very reliable; (2, orange): reliable; (3, yellow): not so reliable; (4, green): not reliable.

It is important to remark that the results obtained by ADAfinder with this (and any other real) dataset are the same than those obtained when computing the results in a manual way.

The situation of ADAclassifier and los2hv is different. These applications are much newer and no

Figure 7: Location of the test sites for the ADAclassifier and los2hv tools.

previous real datasets were at hand, so, at the time of writing this paper, still no actual results based on real datasets were available. Nonetheless, the University of Alicante, in cooperation with the University of Florence, and using datasets kindly provided by this last institution, is currently and actively testing these tools. The areas covered are Zeri, Abbaddia San Salvatore and Campiglia Marittima, all of them located in Italy (see Figure 7).

Unlike formal tests, where it is possible to predict the outcomes of the tools because of a controlled set of input data, real datasets pose a much more difficult challenge due to the complexity of the information they contain. Therefore, the expertise of seasoned experts in the field is required; validating the correctness of the output is a slow task; furthermore, obtaining data to check the six different deformation processes is not easy—inventories, for instance, are very hard to find.

However, and although it is not possible to publish any definitive conclusions now, the preliminary results obtained up to now are very promising—confirming, at least for the time being, the positive results of the formal tests.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The toolset presented in this paper, in either of its three incarnations (library, command-line or GUI application) is an efficient way to automate the detection and classification of ADAs in very short times, freeing their users from the error-prone, manual process required when a GIS tool is used to put into practice

the underlying methodologies—(Barra et al., 2017; Tomás et al., 2018). For instance, the ADAfinder tool, for which former references existed, is at least 10 times faster than a regular GIS operator.

The tools are also flexible, being able to adapt themselves to variations in the format of the input shapefiles thanks to the use of the so-called ”read-map files.”

Speed, flexibility and adequate GUI interfaces make the toolset a very apt tool for research activities, where different scenarios—usually defined by variations on the input parameters—may change the results. On the other side, the availability of the command-line versions of the tools makes possible to integrate them in more production-oriented environments, thanks to the use of option files. Furthermore, it is possible to use the toolset as a black box to include it in higher level software components, since C++ classes have been included in the library implementing the logic of the three applications. Last, but not least, the tools, in their GUI versions, may be integrated quite easily in either ArcGIS or Quantum GIS—there is no need to modify the source code; this may be done using the mechanisms provided by these GIS tools. In this way, the applications become an extra set of tools available in the regular work environment of a GIS operator.

The toolset has undergone a very strict testing process, using either real datasets and the comparison of manual and automated results to check their validity or synthetic ones when these were not available—that is, for ADAclassifier and los2hv. In this case, however, the software is being actively tested nowadays, and, although no results are available yet, the partial outcomes are promising, thus confirming, at the time being, the positive results of the formal validation process.

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